

INVESTIGATION OF PHENOL, FLAVONOID AND ANTIOXIDANT COMPOUND LEVELS (IC50) OF DRIED AND FRESH MANGROVE (*RHIZOPORA RACEMOSA*) LEAVES EXTRACED THROUGH INFUSING TECHNIQUE AS HERBAL DRINK BASE

SUTRISNO ADI PRAYITNO *

Food Technology Department, Agriculture Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik, JL. Sumatera No. 101. Gresik Kota Baru (GKB) East Java – Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: sutrisnoadi2007@umg.ac.id

ANDI RAHMAD RAHIM

Aquaculture Department, Agriculture Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik, JL. Sumatera No. 101. Gresik Kota Baru (GKB) East Java – Indonesia.

DWI RETNANINGTYAS UTAMI

Food Technology Department, Agriculture Faculty, Universitas Muhammadiyah Gresik, JL. Sumatera No. 101. Gresik Kota Baru (GKB) East Java – Indonesia.

Abstract

Mangrove plants (*Rhizophora racemosa*) are one type of plant that has the potential for health, such as to overcome diarrhea, nausea, and skin diseases, and can even be used as antimicrobials and antioxidants. The use of mangrove leaves as a functional ingredient can be associated with various secondary metabolites such as steroids, saponins, tannins, phenols, flavonoids, and antioxidants; besides that, there are also magnesium, sodium, potassium, calcium, and so on. This study focused on determining the total phenol content (TPC), total flavonoid content (TFC), and antioxidants (IC50) in the infusion extract of dry and fresh mangrove leaves. The method used in this research is infused extraction (steeping). The materials used are fresh mangrove leaves and dry leaves after drying in an oven. The data obtained is then discussed descriptively based on the average obtained in the calculation. The results showed that the type or condition of the leaves used influenced the TPC, TFC, and antioxidants as a form of secondary metabolite compounds. Oven drying can produce higher levels of secondary metabolites than fresh leaf infusions (TPC, 36 mg GAE/g; TFC 4.12 mg QE/g; IC50 225.706 ppm). Dry leaf extraction has better potential to produce secondary metabolic compounds and antioxidants. Secondary metabolite compounds can play a role in human health, such as being used in the development of simplisa (tea) beverage products with various formulations. The choice of extraction method and type of solvent is highly recommended for the purpose of further research because it adjusts to the interests of the research. It is recommended in the manufacture of functional beverages (tea) from mangrove leaves to add other sources of ingredients such as dried lemon or mint leaves, so that the resulting flavor is fresher and provides a better liking assessment.

Index Term- Mangrove, Bioactive, Phenol, Flavonoid, Antioxidant, Infusa.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mangrove plants (*Rhizophora racemosa*) are often found in Indonesia, especially in coastal areas [1]. The habitat of this plant also depends on climate, substrate in the soil, salinity conditions [2], drastic climate change (increased rainfall, storms, and increased sea surface temperatures) also affects life in mangroves [3]. These plants have many

economic values that are very useful for human life [4]. Mangrove plants play a role in protecting against waves and providing habitat for reptiles, birds, fish, and so on [5]. Mangrove plants have an important value in their habitat [6] and can be used as plants that can maintain environmental balance [7].

The roots of mangrove plants protect coastal areas, increase the marine food chain, improve water quality [8], and maintain ecosystem balance [9]. Mangrove plant wood can be used as charcoal, firewood, poles, or roofs in making houses, kitchen utensils, furniture, and so on [10].

Plants generally have various sources of active compounds that are potentially good for humans [11]. Biochemicals are not only found in plants but also in animals including marine products [12]. Secondary metabolites have diverse biological activities with unique molecular structures [13]. *Rhizophora racemosa* plants also have potential in secondary metabolite compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids [14], tannins [15], phenolic acids, quinones, tetralones, benzopyranone xanthenes [13].

This plant also plays a role in the field of medicine and the field of toxicology and is a very important ecological field [16]. Mangrove plants are believed to have health properties that can cure various diseases [17], including rheumatism, diabetes, snake bites [18], asthma, skin diseases, sore throat, diarrhea, fever, worms, and others [19]. Active compounds in mangrove plants also have a role in other health fields, such as anti-bacterial, anti-protozoa, antiviral [20], and anti-function agents [21], antibiotics [22]. In another study, it was also mentioned that this mangrove plant also contained several other active compounds, such as strong immunosuppressants, antiparasitics, anticytotoxic and antioxidants [23].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials, tools and method: The main materials used in this study are wet and dry mangrove leaves, distilled water, gallic acid, Ethanol P.A, Na₂ CO₃, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, NaNO₂, AlCl₃, NaOH, and DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl). The tools used are test tubes, Erlenmeyer, measuring cups, volume pipettes, micropipettes, filter paper, spectrophotometer, vortex, and incubator. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative with testing of each parameter carried out twice and then the results are averaged and tabulated.

2.2 Mangrove leaves drying: Fresh mangrove leaves as much as 1 kg are washed thoroughly with running water and drained for 20 minutes. Then dried in the wind for 2 hours and continued with oven drying for 12 hours at a temperature of 70° C. After drying, the simplisia was coarsely crushed (not in powder form), and the results were stored in an airtight container.

2.3 Infusa Extraction: This study uses two types of mangrove leaf conditions: dry leaves and wet leaves. A total of 100 grams each of dry leaves that have been prepared previously and fresh leaves (which have been chopped) are put into an infusion vessel

(stacked pot) and filled with 1000 mL of water as a medium. Heat until it reaches a temperature of 90 °C for 15 minutes, if the temperature and time have been reached turn off the fireplace and filter to get infusa extract (juice) pack it in a closed container, and store it for a while to cool, and do water testing of the infuse extract.

2.4 Investigation of Total Phenol level [24]: A total of 0.025 g of gallic acid was weighed analytically in weighing paper and then put in a 100 ml *beaker glass*. Added 0.2 ml ethanol p.a and then added distilled water to reach a volume of 100 ml (obtained 250 ppm gallic acid solution). Then homogenized with shaking. This solution was then used as gallic acid mother solution. A standard solution of gallic acid with various concentrations of 50; 100; 150; 200, and 250 ppm was made by taking each gallic acid mother solution as much as 0; 2; 4; 6; and 8 ml and put into a 10 ml volumetric flask and then added distilled water to reach a volume of 10 ml. A total of 0.4 mL of standard gallic acid solution was analytically pipetted, then put into a 10 mL flask and then added 0.4 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and then shaken. After five minutes, 4 ml of 7% Na₂ CO₃ (b/v) was added and aquabides were added until it reached a volume of 10 ml and then shaken and incubated for 90 minutes at 23°C. Measurement of the absorbance of the gallic acid standard solution at λ-max with a spectrophotometer (obtained maximum absorbance at λ 760 nm). Preparation of a standard curve between absorbance (as y-axis) and concentration (as x-axis) with units of ppm. Calculated the equation of the linear regression curve resulting in the equation: $Y = ax + b$; Y = sample absorbance, x = sample concentration (ppm).

2.5 Investigation of Total Flavonoid Levels [24]: Analysis of mangrove extract using spectrophotometry. The standard used is quercetin with concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 ppm. 1 ml sample infuse extract was added with 4 ml distilled water and 0.3 ml NaNO₂ 5% into a test tube and vortexed until homogeneous, then incubated for five minutes. After 5 minutes, 0.3 ml of AlCl₃ was added and re-incubated for 6 minutes, and 2 ml of 1 M NaOH and distilled water were added to reach a volume of 10 ml and vortexed until homogeneous. The absorbance value of the sample was measured with a wavelength of 510 nm using the linear equation $y = ax + b$ where the x-axis is the concentration and the y-axis is the absorbance.

2.6 Antioxidant Investigation [25]: Analysis of antioxidant activity (IC₅₀) of infusa extract was carried out by DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) method using a spectrophotometer. The concentrations used were 25, 50, 75, 100 and 125 ppm. The analysis procedure is to put 2 ml of infused extract sample into a test tube and add 1 ml of 200 μM DPPH solution, then vortexed until homogeneous and incubated for 30 minutes. The absorbance value of the sample was measured at a wavelength of 517 nm with a linear line equation $y = ax + b$, where the y-axis is the absorbance of the sample and the x-axis is the concentration of the standard used.

Research Parameters: Several parameters that would be analyzed in this research are total phenol content (TPC) [24], total flavonoid content (TFC) [24], and Antioxidant (IC₅₀) [25].

2.7 Data Analysis: The data obtained were analyzed by describing the analysis results based on the average value obtained for each parameter.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To obtain active compounds as secondary metabolites in natural materials, appropriate extraction techniques are needed. Extraction gives good results and correlates to the compounds present in the extracted material. The choice of method is adjusted to the purpose and function of the extraction. From the results of the study can be seen the difference between the results of infusa extraction on fresh mangrove leaves and mangrove leaves that have undergone drying. Table 1 presents the results of the study.

Table 1: Average Results of Compound Investigation of Infuse Extracts

Infusa Treatment	Analysis Parameters		
	TPC (mg GAE/g)	TFC (Mg QE/g)	Antioxidant (IC50) (ppm)
Fresh leaf infusion extract	32	2.65	230.75
Dried leaf infusion extract	36	4.12	225.71

TPC= Total Pgenol Content; TFC=Total Flavonoid Content mocaf; IC50= Inhibition contrentation

According to the table 1, the use of mangrove leaves with different physical conditions (wet and dry) has an influence on the test parameters, namely on TPC, TFC and IC50. Dry mangrove leaves have higher values on test parameters compared to wet leaves. The explanation of the research results is as follows.

3.1 Total Phenol Content (TPC)

Phenol is a bioactive compound that is classified as a secondary metabolite. This compound is found in natural materials both plants and animals including marine products. Phenolic compounds in natural materials are influenced by the physical conditions of the original material. Wet leaves and leaves will produce different phenol levels. Also revealed that in materials that undergo the drying process, affect the composition of phenolic compounds in the extract on the leaves, which has an impact on the amount of antioxidant compounds [26]. Based on **Table 1**, there are differences in infusa levels in dry and wet leaves. Dry leaves have a lower water content than wet leaves. In dry leaves, this is very beneficial in the extraction process of phenol compounds. Low water content can be a barrier to organic solvents used in the extraction process. This tendency will produce higher phenol compounds (secondary metabolites) compared to wet mangrove leaves. This is supported by the research of [27] which states that the process of extracting phenolic compounds roughly in dry leaves provides a more effective process than the extraction of wet leaves because low water conditions in the material can be used as a medium to facilitate the extraction of higher phenolic compounds. Conversely, infusion extraction using wet leaves will provide lower phenolic concentrations obtained because the water contained in mangrove leaves can reduce the solubility of phenolic compounds in organic solvents, and can reduce the efficiency of

infusion extraction. This is in line with the research which states that the extraction of secondary metabolite compounds (phenols) from wet leaves will produce lower yields. This is influenced by the negative effect of water content on the extraction of these phenol compounds Zhang et al (2018).

Another reason that could be the cause of the difference in phenol content is also supported by the review which states that wet and dry physical conditions on leaves can affect the stability and bioavailability of phenol compounds contained in the resulting extract. This also affects the potential of its biological activity. In addition to the type of material as a medium that affects the extraction of phenol compounds, the method of selection in extraction will also affect the final result, especially phenolic compounds [26]. Maceration, infusion, or MAE methods with certain solvents will give different results but also depend on the physical condition of the material (dry or wet). According to a review stated that extraction carried out by ultrasonic methods or techniques can increase phenol content in dry leaves compared to wet leaves [28].

3.2 Total flavonoid content (TFC)

Flavonoids are found in many plant parts such as fruit, seeds, leaves, roots, stems, branches and so on (Sahoo and Marar, 2018). The difference in infuse extraction results in dry and wet mangrove leaves affects the total flavonoids produced. This is also influenced by the extraction method used. The extraction method affects the extraction results. The condition of the material, either wet or dry mangrove leaves, also affects the flavonoid content of the infuse extraction results.

This is supported by a study using ultrasonic extraction that the total flavonoids produced are influenced by the extraction method and the condition or characteristics of the material when extracted [29]. It is also emphasized in the research results that dry leaves when extracted will produce higher total phenol content compared to wet leaves. Because dry leaves allow the process of diffusion and osmosis to occur maximally in the withdrawal of extracted compounds [30]. Meanwhile, wet leaves when extracted will produce lower secondary metabolite compounds because they are affected by water in green tea materials, because water interferes with the process of osmosis and diffusion into the extracted material (affecting the efficiency of flavonoid dissolution) [31].

The difference in mangrove leaves in wet or dry conditions influences the levels of flavonoid compounds produced. Flavonoid compounds are more stable in the state of dry leaves and easily come out of the cells so as to facilitate and speed up the extraction process. This is also supported by the drying process of ginkgo biloba leaves which can increase the concentration of flavonoids which are more stable [32]. Whereas in wet mangrove leaves, the water content affects the stability of flavonoid compounds because water in the material contributes to flavonoids which are sensitive to temperature and humidity. This is supported by a study on herbal plants that have lower flavonoid levels in extracted wet leaves because a certain amount of water causes unwanted chemical changes in flavonoid compounds [33].

3.3 Antioxidant (IC₅₀)

In choosing the type of material of dry mangrove leaves or wet mangrove leaves in infusa extraction, it must consider intrinsic or extrinsic factors in order to obtain optimal antioxidant results (IC₅₀). Antioxidant activity (IC₅₀) in infusion extracts has differences. It is influenced by several factors including water content, stability of antioxidant compounds, as well as the extraction method used, and so on.

The relationship with water content is the amount of water content contained in the material and affects the total antioxidants in infusa extracts (dry and wet mangrove leaves). Dry mangrove leaves certainly have a lower water content than wet mangrove leaves. Dry leaf extraction will dry a high level of antioxidants because it affects the compounds that play a role in antioxidants including tannins or flavonoids contained in mangrove leaves.

This is supported by research on mangrove species that extract dry leaves and show higher flavonoid and antioxidant levels compared to extracts of wet leaf mangrove species [34]. The extraction of wet mangrove leaves still has a high water content and affects the process and efficiency in the extraction of compounds that have antioxidant potential.

This water affects the degradation or damage to bioactive compounds present in wet mangrove leaves during the extraction process. In a study of wet mangrove extracts, it was mentioned that antioxidants have low stability when compared to the stability of extracts in dry leaves. In dry leaves, the supporting compounds of antioxidants are easier to extract and produce higher yields [35].

In addition, the drying process affects total antioxidants and increases their stability [36]. In contrast to wet leaves that are directly extracted, water in the material (wet mangrove leaves) can degrade or destroy active compounds during the storage or processing of the material [37].

The extraction method also affects the level of antioxidants produced. Infusion extraction is different from other extractions. In infuse extraction using a solvent in the form of water, while in research supports high antioxidant activity due to extracting materials with organic solvents (methanol) on mangrove leaves [38]. In addition, the increase in IC₅₀ levels is supported by an increase in total phenols and flavonoids present in the extracted material [39].

4. CONCLUSION

Extraction with infuse technique influences the total phenol, total flavonoid, and total antioxidant (IC₅₀) in mangrove leaves. Mangrove leaves that undergo oven drying have higher secondary metabolic compounds and antioxidants compared to extraction with wet leaves. The result of analysis each parameters on dry leaves are, TPC; 36 mg GAE/g; TFC 4.12 mg QE/g; and IC₅₀ 225.706 ppm.

References

- 1) A. Mohti, I. Parlan, and H. O. Contents, "Research and Development Activities Towards Sustainable Management of Mangroves in Peninsular Malaysia," *For. Environ. Devison, For. Res. Inst. Malaysia*, pp. 373–390, 2014, doi: 10.1007/978-1-4614-8582-7.
- 2) M. H. Zakaria and J. S. Bujang, *Status of*. 2020.
- 3) H. Omar and M. A. Misman, *Extend and Distribution of Mangroves in Malaysia*. 2020.
- 4) T. N. T. Hamzah, M. Ozturk, V. Altay, and K. R. Hakeem, *Insights into the bioactive compounds of endophytic fungi in mangroves*, vol. 1. INC, 2020. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-819541-3.00015-3.
- 5) A. Chiavaroli *et al.*, "Identification of Chemical Profiles and Biological Properties of *Rhizophora racemosa* G. Mey. Extracts Obtained by Different Methods and Solvents Annalisa," *Antioxidants*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1–37, 2020.
- 6) C. P. N. Tshiaba, A. N. Mbaya, A. Z. Idrissa, Antoine Djamba Mumba, S. N. Luyindula, and R. K. N. Mwange, "Comparative analysis of three vegetative propagation techniques of *Rhizophora racemosa* G.F.W. Meyer for ex-situ conservation," *GSC Adv. Res. Rev.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 072–087, 2023, doi: 10.30574/gscarr.2023.17.1.0374.
- 7) L. Cherigo, D. López, C. Spadafora, L. C. Mejia, and S. Martínez-Luis, "Exploring the Biomedical Potential of Endophytic Fungi Isolated from Panamanian Mangroves," *Nat. Prod. Commun.*, vol. 19, no. 1, 2024, doi: 10.1177/1934578X241228152.
- 8) R. Othman, R. Ramya, Z. M. Baharuddin, K. S. H. Y. Hashim, and M. Yaman, "Ecological indicator agents for inorganic contaminants state monitoring through *Sonneratia alba*, *Avicennia alba* and *Rhizophora apiculata*," *J. Teknol.*, vol. 77, no. 30, pp. 111–118, 2015, doi: 10.11113/jt.v77.6874.
- 9) W. M. Bandaranayake, "Bioactivities, bioactive compounds and chemical constituents of mangrove plants," *Wetl. Ecol. Manag.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 421–452, 2002, doi: 10.1023/A:1021397624349.
- 10) R. Ramya, S. Kamoon, F. A. Mohd Hatta, W. S. H. Wan Sulaiman, N. H. Mohd Latiff, and R. Othman, "A Study on an Active Functional Group and Antimicrobial Properties From *Rhizophora apiculata* Extracts Used in Traditional Malay as Medicine," *Malaysian Appl. Biol.*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 153–160, 2023, doi: 10.55230/mabjournal.v52i4.d180.
- 11) H. X. Liu *et al.*, "Cytosporins A-D, novel benzophenone derivatives from the endophytic fungus: *Cytospora rhizophorae* A761," *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, vol. 17, no. 9, pp. 2346–2350, 2019, doi: 10.1039/c8ob03223h.
- 12) E. S. Izuogu *et al.*, "Screening of secondary metabolites produced by a mangrove-derived *Nigrospora* species an endophytic fungus isolated from *Rhizophora racemosa* for antioxidant and antimicrobial properties," *GSC Adv. Res. Rev.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 047–060, 2023, doi: 10.30574/gscarr.2023.15.2.0133.
- 13) K. Sopalun, W. Laosripaiboon, A. Wachirachakarn, and S. Iamtham, "Biological potential and chemical composition of bioactive compounds from endophytic fungi associated with thai mangrove plants," *South African J. Bot.*, vol. 141, pp. 66–76, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.sajb.2021.04.031.
- 14) S. Mitra, N. Naskar, and P. Chaudhuri, "A review on potential bioactive phytochemicals for novel therapeutic applications with special emphasis on mangrove species," *Phytomedicine Plus*, vol. 1, no. 4, p. 100107, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.phyplu.2021.100107.
- 15) A. Egwunatum, N. . Ndulue, U. Onejeme, and C. Obasi, "Evaluation of Industrial and Thermal Properties of Mangrove Tree (*Rhizophora racemosa*) Tannin on Variegated Wood Waste," *Proceeding first Fac. Agric. Int. Conf.*, pp. 165–170, 2023.

- 16) I. Süntar, "Importance of ethnopharmacological studies in drug discovery: role of medicinal plants," *Phytochem. Rev.*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 1199–1209, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11101-019-09629-9.
- 17) B. Angalabiri-Owei, J. Isirima, B. Angalabiri-Owei, J. Isirima, B. Angalabiri-Owei, and J. Isirima, "Evaluation of the lethal dose of the methanol extract of rhizophora racemosa leaf using Karbers method," *African J. Cell. Pathol.*, vol. 2, no. 5, pp. 65–68, 2014, doi: 10.5897/ajcpath14.009.
- 18) C. Musara, E. B. Aladejana, and S. M. Mudywa, "Review of botany, nutritional, medicinal, pharmacological properties and phytochemical constituents of bruguiera gymnorhiza (L.) Lam, (Rhizophoraceae)," *J. Pharm. Nutr. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 123–132, 2020, doi: 10.29169/1927-5951.2020.10.04.1.
- 19) T. Sur, A. Hazra, A. Hazra, and D. Bhattacharyya, "Antioxidant and hepatoprotective properties of Indian Sunderban mangrove Bruguiera gymnorhiza L. leave," *J. Basic Clin. Pharm.*, vol. 7, no. 3, p. 75, 2016, doi: 10.4103/0976-0105.183262.
- 20) R. D. Cadamuro *et al.*, "Bioactive compounds from mangrove endophytic fungus and their uses for microorganism control," *J. Fungi*, vol. 7, no. 6, 2021, doi: 10.3390/jof7060455.
- 21) I. Lagunes, H. Lumbreras-Martínez, C. Espinoza, J. M. Padrón, J. López-Portillo, and Á. Trigos, "Diversity and bioactivity of sediment-associated fungi from a mangrove forest in Mexico with different conservation conditions," *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 379–387, 2023, doi: 10.3856/vol51-issue3-fulltext-2971.
- 22) S. L. Jia, Z. Chi, G. L. Liu, Z. Hu, and Z. M. Chi, "Fungi in mangrove ecosystems and their potential applications," *Crit. Rev. Biotechnol.*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 852–864, 2020, doi: 10.1080/07388551.2020.1789063.
- 23) A. Chatterjee and J. Abraham, *Mangrove endophytes: A rich source of bioactive substances*. INC, 2020. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-819532-1.00002-0.
- 24) S. . Prayitno, L. Lestari, D. Utami, and N. Salsabila, "Food Science and Technology Journal Evaluation of Phytochemicals And Antioxidant Activity (IC50) of Bintaro Fruit Ethanol Extract (Cerberaodollam L.)," *Food Sci. Technol. J. Eval.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2021, doi: DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.25139/fst.v4i1.3686> effects,.
- 25) S. A. Prayitno and A. R. Rahim, "The Comparison of Extracts (Ethanol And Aquos Solvents) Muntingia calabura Leaves on Total Phenol, Flavonid And Antioxidant (Ic50) Properties," *Kontribusi (Research Dissem. Community Dev.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 319–325, 2020, doi: 10.30587/kontribusi.v3i2.1451.
- 26) L. Barros, M. Dueñas, I. C. F. R. Ferreira, P. Baptista, and C. Santos-Buelga, "Phenolic acids determination by HPLC-DAD-ESI/MS in sixteen different Portuguese wild mushrooms species," *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 1076–1079, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.fct.2009.01.039.
- 27) L. Wang, C. L. Weller, and S. . Cuppett, "Factors influencing total phenolic content, antioxidant capacity, and stability of partitioned cranberry products," *J. Agric. Food Chem*, vol. 70, no. 49, pp. 15560–15569, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.2c06502>.
- 28) B. Ranković and M. Kosanić, "Lichen Secondary Metabolites," *Lichen Second. Metab.*, pp. 1–29, 2019, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-16814-8.
- 29) J. Čvorović, L. Ziberna, S. Fornasaro, F. Tramer, and S. Passamonti, "Bioavailability of flavonoids: The role of cell membrane transporters," *Polyphenols Mech. Action Hum. Heal. Dis.*, pp. 295–320, 2018, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-813006-3.00022-2.
- 30) P. Ebrahimi, D. Mihaylova, C. M. Marangon, L. Grigoletto, and A. Lante, "Impact of Sample Pretreatment and Extraction Methods on the Bioactive Compounds of Sugar Beet (Beta vulgaris L.) Leaves," *Molecules*, vol. 27, no. 22, pp. 2–19, 2022, doi: 10.3390/molecules27228110.

- 31) M. Usman, M. Nakagawa, and S. Cheng, "Emerging Trends in Green Extraction Techniques for Bioactive Natural Products," *Processes*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 2–31, 2023, doi: 10.3390/pr11123444.
- 32) A. Šali, L. Šepi, I. Turkalj, and B. Zeli, "Comparative Analysis of Enzyme-, Ultrasound-, Mechanical-, and Chemical-Assisted Extraction of Biflavonoids from Ginkgo Leaves," vol. 12, no. 982, pp. 2–14, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12050982>.
- 33) A. Vega-Galvez *et al.*, "Assessment of Bio-Compounds Content, Antioxidant Activity, and Neuroprotective Effect of Red Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *Capitata rubra*) Processed by Convective Drying at Different Temperatures," *Antioxidants*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 2–20, 2023, doi: 10.3390/antiox12091789.
- 34) A. Adrien, A. Bonnet, D. Dufour, S. Baudouin, T. Maugard, and N. Bridiau, "Anticoagulant activity of sulfated ulvan isolated from the green macroalga *Ulva rigida*," *Mar. Drugs*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 14–16, 2019, doi: 10.3390/md17050291.
- 35) H. Wang, L. Shu, Z.-Y. Su, F. Fuentes, J.-H. Lee, and A.-N. T. Kong, "Send Orders of Reprints at reprints@benthamscience.org Anti-Cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry Plants vs. Cancer: A Review on Natural Phytochemicals in Preventing and Treating Cancers and Their Druggability," vol. 12, pp. 1281–1305, 2012.
- 36) M. Simões, R. N. Bennett, and E. A. S. Rosa, "Understanding antimicrobial activities of phytochemicals against multidrug resistant bacteria and biofilms," *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 746–757, 2009, doi: 10.1039/b821648g.
- 37) L. Chiang, L. Ng, L. Liu, D. Shieh, and C. Lin, "S-2003-42797," vol. 69, pp. 705–709, 2003.
- 38) K. Patrick-Iwuanyanwu, E. N. Onyeike, and A. Adhikari, "Journal of Natural Products Isolation , identification and characterization of gallic acid derivatives from leaves of *Tapinanthus bangwensis*," vol. 7, no. June, pp. 14–19, 2014.
- 39) S. P. Widyawati, T. D. W. Budianta, F. A. Kusuma, and E. L. Wijaya, "Difference of solvent polarity to phytochemical content and antioxidant activity of *Pluchea indica* less leaves extracts," *Int. J. Pharmacogn. Phytochem. Res.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 850–855, 2014.